

MECHANICAL RELIABILITY OF INORGANIC THIN FILM PHOTOVOLTAICS INTEGRATED WITH COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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Keywords: *multifunctional composites, solar cells, residual stresses*

1 Introduction

Successful integration of solar cells as power sources in aerospace applications requires resilience to external mechanical loads while maintaining performance. This paper studies the mechanical and failure properties of brittle thin film photovoltaics and the reliability of photovoltaic cells integrated onto composite laminates.

The residual stresses and the mechanical strength of inorganic thin photovoltaic films were quantified for the first time so that functional and material failure predictions could be made when they are integrated with composite laminates [1,2]. The performance of photovoltaics was monitored while integrated onto a composite laminate and subjected to uniaxial tensile loading. The inorganic photovoltaic films consisted of a top electrode, a Transparent Conductive Oxide (TCO) layer, a silicon (Si) p-n junction diode, and a thick aluminum substrate.

2 Materials and Experiments

The mean residual stress of the thin photovoltaic films was measured from the blister geometrical characteristics of straight and telephone cord delaminations. Straight blisters formed in the Si layer when the TCO was absent. When combined,

the latter contributed additional residual compressive stress, leading to the formation of telephone cord type blisters. The buckling and mean residual stresses of a straight blister were calculated as [3]:

$$\sigma_B = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \frac{E}{(1-\nu^2)} \left(\frac{h}{b}\right)^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_R = \frac{3}{4} \sigma_B \left(\frac{H^2}{h^2} + 1\right) \quad (2)$$

where σ_B is the buckling stress, σ_R is the mean residual stress, E is the elastic modulus, ν is Poisson's ratio, h is the film thickness, b is the half-width and H is the height of the blister.

The residual stress of a telephone cord blister is given by the same expression as the straight blister, multiplied by a correction factor [4]:

$$\sigma_B = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \frac{\bar{E}}{(1-\nu^2)} \left(\frac{h}{b}\right)^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_{R,TCD} = 1.08\sigma_R = 1.08 \left(\frac{3}{4} \sigma_B \left(\frac{H^2}{h^2} + 1\right)\right) \quad (4)$$

where \bar{E} is the composite elastic modulus and $\sigma_{R,TCD}$ is the residual stress of the telephone cord blister.

The stress gradient was calculated from the residual curvature exhibited by freestanding Si monolayer and Si/TCO bi-layer films. The elastic modulus mismatch between the two materials was taken into account in the case of bilayers, which resulted in stress discontinuity at the interface.

The calculation of residual stresses requires the elastic modulus of the two materials. The elastic moduli, as well as the strength values were obtained by performing microscale uniaxial tension tests on Si monolayer and Si-TCO bilayer freestanding strips [5]. The rectangular shape uniaxial tension specimens were produced by fragmentation of the photovoltaic films. Before mechanical testing, they were inspected by a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) to ensure that their surface is crack-free, as shown in Fig. 1.

The applied force in microscale tension experiments was measured by a miniature loadcell. The strain was calculated by Digital Image Correlation (DIC) using in-situ obtained optical images of the surface of the thin films. The two measurements were used to compute the elastic moduli of the two layers in the photovoltaic films.

Finally, thin film photovoltaics were integrated onto carbon fiber composite laminates, during the laminate curing process. Three different laminates were employed with 0° , $0^\circ/90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ fiber directions. Loading the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ composite laminates led to localized cracking and failure of the matrix in the 90° layers, which, in turn, led to damage in the photovoltaic thin films and reduction in cell efficiency. For these reasons, the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ orientation composites were not pursued further.

The performance of the photovoltaics was measured before and after co-curing with the laminate, in order

to assess the effect of curing on the photovoltaic film reliability. The resulting multifunctional composites were subjected to uniaxial tension while cracks forming on the surface of the thin film photovoltaics were monitored by a CCD camera. In addition, the current vs. voltage (I-V) characteristics of the photovoltaics were measured as a function of applied strain, by modeling the photovoltaic cell as a diode and connecting it to a circuit including a variable resistor [6] as:

$$I = I_L - I_D \quad (5)$$

where I is the total current, I_L is the current related to illumination, I_D is the current given by the diode equation which is a function of the output voltage and the ambient temperature. The performance of the photovoltaic cells was quantified by the fill factor (FF), which was calculated by dividing the maximum output power of the photovoltaic with the maximum power of an ideal photovoltaic cell with the same open circuit voltage and short circuit current. The photovoltaic cells used in the present experiments had FF values larger than 0.55.

3 Experimental Results and Discussion

Using the methods described in the previous section, the mean residual stress in the Si monolayer was found to be (-470 ± 110) MPa, while in the Si-TCO bilayer was (-660 ± 90) MPa. Fig. 2 shows the profile analysis of a telephone cord delamination blister.

The residual stress gradient of the Si layer was measured as 275 ± 20 MPa/ μm , while the effective residual stress gradient in the Si/TCO bi-layer was 340 ± 25 MPa/ μm .

The magnitude of the mean compressive residual stress was larger than that of the local tensile stress due to the residual stress gradient, resulting in compressive stress across the entire photovoltaic film thickness. This compressive residual stress is beneficial as it mitigates the severity of externally applied tensile loads.

The tensile strength of the Si layer was 425 ± 75 MPa while of the Si-TCO bi-layer was only 110 ± 25 MPa. Fig. 3 shows a failure cross-section of a Si/TCO bilayer. When compared to the strength of the Si monolayer, the almost four times smaller strength of the Si/TCO bi-layer could be attributed, in part, to the significantly larger stress gradient of the bi-layer, which differed by $2\frac{1}{2}$ times that of the Si monolayer.

Imaging of the ZnO and Si surfaces of the Si-TCO bilayer specimens during the uniaxial testing showed that ZnO was the first film to fracture while the Si layer followed immediately after. Real time optical imaging also revealed a weak interface between the two thin films, with delamination occurring during mechanical testing.

The calculation of the FF before and after co-curing of the photovoltaics with the composite laminates resulted in less than 0.3% reduction of the photovoltaics' performance. Fig. 4 shows the I-V curves before and after co-curing a photovoltaic with a composite laminate, as well as the rectangular areas which define the maximum power in each case. The FFs of the integrated photovoltaics were also calculated when exposed to constant power light source, in order to investigate whether a degradation associated with a temperature increase due to prolonged light exposure had taken place

[7,8]. I-V curves for exposure after 0, 9, 15 and 24 hr revealed no change in performance.

The calculation of the mean compressive residual stress in the Si/TCO bi-layer, when integrated on the laminate showed an increase of approximately 20%, while the bucking stress remained constant. The increase in residual stresses indicates a build-up during the curing cycle, which acts beneficially against external tensile loads.

During loading of the multi-functional composites, transverse cracks formed in the TCO and Si layers. The fracture of the TCO thin film preceded that of Si but did not result in degradation on the solar cell performance. Fig. 5a shows crack initiation on the ZnO surface at 0.28% strain and Fig. 5b shows the ZnO fragmented surface at 1.20% strain. Reduction in power output, defined by the maximum rectangular area under the I-V curve, was observed once fragmentation initiated in the Si layer. Cracking throughout the thickness of the Si/TCO thin films resulted in discontinuities in the photovoltaic circuit. Fig. 6 shows cracks in the ZnO layer, in the transverse to the loading direction, for a photovoltaic integrated onto a $\pm 45^\circ$ composite laminate. The cracks in the $\pm 45^\circ$ direction developed upon laminate failure and led to spallation and precipitous drop in the performance of the photovoltaic cell.

Similarly, a reduction in power output of a photovoltaic integrated onto a 0° composite laminate initiated after cracks appeared on both the ZnO and Si thin films. The I-V curves at different loading steps are shown in Fig. 7a, while the corresponding FFs (for strain larger than 0.6%) are shown in Fig.

7b; for instance, upon 1.5% strain, the FF of the integrated photovoltaic dropped to about 35%.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the support by the Air Force Office for Scientific Research through Grant FA9550-12-1-0209, with Dr. B.L. Lee as the program manager.

References

- [1] J.L. Maung, T.H. Hahn and Y.S. Ju “Multifunctional integration of thin-film silicon solar cells on carbon-fiber-reinforced epoxy composites”. *Solar Energy*, Vol. 84, pp. 450–458, 2010.
- [2] J.W. Jeon, J.S. Im, S. Park, L. Feng, J.H. Jin, J.S. Kim, J.H. Ko, S.C. Yang, B.S. Bae and K.S. Lim “Flexible amorphous silicon solar cells on glass-fabric reinforced composite films in the superstrate configuration”. *Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC)*, Hawaiian Convention Center Honolulu, HI, USA, Vol. 35, pp. 001151–001154, 2010.
- [3] J.W. Hutchinson and Z. Suo “Mixed mode cracking in layered materials”. *Advances in Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 29, p. 63-191, 1992.
- [4] M.W. Moon, H.M. Jensen, J.W. Hutchinson, K.H. Oh and A.G. Evans “The characterization of telephone cord buckling of compressed thin films on substrates”. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, Vol. 50, pp. 2355-2377, 2002.
- [5] K. Jonnalagadda, I. Chasiotis, S. Yagnamurthy, J. Lambros, R. Polcawich, J. Pulskamp and M. Dubey,

“Experimental Investigation of Strain Rate Dependence in Nanocrystalline Pt Films,” *Experimental Mechanics*, Vol. 50, 1, pp. 25-35, 2010.

- [6] G. Boyle, *Renewable Energy: Power for a Sustainable Future*, Oxford University Press-The Open University, UK, Chapter 3: SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAICS, pp. 66-83, 2004.
- [7] S. Pingel, D. Kosnishaov, O. Frank, T. Geipel, Y. Zemen, B. Striner and J. Berhold, “Initial Degradation of Industrial Silicon Solar Cells in Solar Panels”, *25th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition /5th World Conference on Photovoltaic Energy Conversion*, Valencia, Spain, Session 4AV.3.20, pp. 4027-4032, 2010.
- [8] D.L. Staebler and C.R. Wronski, “Reversible conductivity changes in discharge-produced amorphous Si”, *Applied Physics Letters*, Vol. 31, Issue 4, pp. 292-294, 1977.

Fig. 1 A Si monolayer uniaxial tension specimen (narrow strip) attached to a wide grip.

Fig. 2 Profile of a telephone cord delamination blister using a confocal laser microscope.

Fig. 3 Failure cross-section of a freestanding bilayer strip after tension testing.

Fig. 4 I-V curves of a photovoltaic before and after co-curing with a composite laminate.

Fig. 5 Fragmentation of a Si photovoltaic attached to a $\pm 45^\circ$ composite laminate. Uniaxial tension was applied in the horizontal direction.

Fig. 6a Crack initiation in a Si photovoltaic attached to a 0° composite laminate. Uniaxial tension was applied in the horizontal direction.

Fig. 6a Fragmentation of a Si photovoltaic attached to a 0° composite laminate at 1.20% strain. Uniaxial tension was applied in the horizontal direction.

Fig. 7a I-V curves of a Si photovoltaic attached to a 0° composite laminate.

Fig. 7b Fill factor vs. strain for a Si photovoltaic attached to a 0° composite laminate.